

E-LEARNING AND ITS ORGANIZATION

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ABSTRACT

This article provides detailed information about the e-learning system, its advantages and disadvantages, its types, as well as ways to organize it.

The term e-learning comprises a lot more than online learning, virtual learning, distributed learning, networked or web-based learning. As the letter “e” in e-learning stands for the word “electronic”, it would incorporate all educational activities that are carried out by individuals or groups working online or offline, and synchronously or asynchronously via networked or standalone computers and other electronic devices. It is one of the means that supports the educational process and its transformation from the stage of indoctrination to the stage of creativity, interaction and skill development, and collects all electronic forms of teaching and learning, where the latest methods are used in the fields of teaching, publishing and entertainment by adopting computers, storage media and networks. The rapid transfers in the field of technology have led to the emergence of new patterns of

learning and education, which have further entrenched the concept of individual or self-education, whereby the learner continues his learning according to his energy, ability and speed of his learning according to his previous experiences and skills. E-learning is one of these evolving patterns of so-called distance learning in general, and computer-based education in particular. E-learning mainly relies on computers and networks for transferring knowledge and skills. Its applications include online learning, computer learning, virtual classrooms and digital collaboration. Online tutorial content, audio tapes, videos and discs are offered. Also, we can say understanding e-Learning is simple. E-Learning is learning utilizing electronic technologies to access educational curriculum outside of a traditional classroom. In most cases E-Learning refers to a course, program or degree delivered completely online. There

are many terms used to describe learning that is delivered online, via the internet, ranging from Distance Education, to computerized electronic learning, online learning, internet learning and many others. We define e-Learning as courses that are specifically delivered via the internet to somewhere other than the classroom where the professor is teaching. It is not a course delivered via a DVD or CD-ROM, video tape or over a television channel. It is interactive in that you can also communicate with your teachers, professors or other students in your class. Sometimes it is delivered live, where you can “electronically” raise your hand and interact in real time and sometimes it is a lecture that has been prerecorded.

What is e-Learning? E-learning unites two main areas, learning and technology. Learning is a cognitive process for achieving knowledge, and technology is an enabler of the learning process, meaning that technology is used like any other tool in the education praxis, as is a pencil or a notebook, for example. Although this seems quite simplistic and logical, a pencil is more technologically transparent tool, and its use may therefore seem more natural to many. Furthermore, technology underpins other problematic situations because it includes various dimensions. E-learning systems aggregate various tools, such as writing technologies, communication technologies, visualization, and storage. For these reasons, researchers and scientists have sought to transform e-learning systems into technically transparent tool, like a pencil or notebook. E-Learning is an interactive learning system that provides the learner with the use of communication and information technologies and depends on an integrated

digital electronic environment that displays courses across electronic networks, provides guidance and guidance, organizes tests as well as managing and evaluating resources and processes. The importance of e-learning lies in solving the problem of the knowledge explosion and the increasing demand for education and expanding opportunities for admission to education, in addition to enabling training and education of workers without leaving their jobs and contributing to breaking psychological barriers between the teacher and the learner as well as satisfying the needs and characteristics of the learner while raising the return on investment by reducing the cost of education.

ONLINE EDUCATION. Online education is a flexible instructional delivery system that encompasses any kind of learning that takes place via the Internet. Online learning gives educators an opportunity to reach students who may not be able to enroll in a traditional classroom course and supports students who need to work on their own schedule and at their own pace. The quantity of distance learning and online degrees in most disciplines is large and increasing rapidly. Schools and institutions that offer online learning are also increasing in number. Students pursuing degrees via the online approach must be selective to ensure that their coursework is done through a respected and credentialed institution.

RATIONALE FOR CONSIDERING ONLINE EDUCATION. Online education has become a viable and exciting method for instructional delivery in the global business society that runs on a 24/7 schedule (24 hours a day/7 days a week) because it provides students with great flexibility. With the increased availability of

the Internet and computer technology, students are able to access information anytime and anyplace that would normally be available only through a traditional classroom. Studies have shown that students learn just as effectively in an online classroom as they do in the traditional classroom.

POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EFFECTS OF LEARNING ONLINE. Online education offers many positive benefits since students:

- have flexibility in taking classes and working at their own pace and time
- face no commuting or parking hassles
- learn to become responsible for their own education with information available at their fingertips
- find the submission of assignments easy and convenient

FUTURE OF ONLINE EDUCATION. Online teaching is here to stay. Many students prefer the online classroom since it offers flexibility in their busy schedules. With the proliferation of information and knowledge, students must become lifelong learners in today's world, and online education plays an important role in helping individuals access the learner-centered and self-directed instruction.

With enhanced software, hardware, and Internet access, more options for online education will become available. With student enrollments increasing faster than classrooms can be built, students becoming more proficient with technology, and students pursuing an education that meets

their needs, the future of online education will continue to grow. Online degree programs will become more widely accepted as they become a more common practice.

Conclusion. Online learning has features that cater to these modern learner preferences – hence its rise in popularity. With online learning, your learners can access content anywhere and anytime. They don't need to take time out from their jobs to attend classes E-learning is also cost-effective; companies save a substantial amount on the travel and accommodation costs of both learners and instructors, as well as the venue and materials. No printing helps reduce your carbon footprint, too. Through e-learning, modern learners prefer bite-sized, interactive content. They would rather watch a video or listen to a podcast than read through pages of a manual. E-learning tools enable learning designers to make content interactive. The more engaging the content is, the better the learners remember information. If they enjoy learning, they can able to recall and apply the concepts at work. Also, In face-to-face sessions, every instructor has his or her own method of teaching. Each varies in approach and style and is susceptible to mistakes. You can eliminate these issues with e-learning. Online learning provides consistent and standardized training every time. Each learner goes through the same experience regardless of when and where he or she takes the course.

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